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CHET TILLARNI O'RGANISHNING INTERFAOL USULLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada chet tillarini o'qitish tizimidagi eng samarali usullardan biri bo'lgan interfaol usul muhokama qilinadi. Interfaol o'qitish usuli chet tillarini o'rganishda motivatsiyani oshiradi, o'quvchilar o'quv jarayonida o'zlarini qulayroq his qiladilar. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqolada ko'rib chiqilgan barcha usullar va usullar muloqot qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi, jamoada ishlashga va bir-birini tinglashga o'rgatadi, shuningdek, muayyan pedagogik muammoni hal qilishga hissa qo'shadi. Taqdim etilgan materialga asoslanib, biz shunday xulosaga keldik: interfaol o'qitish usuli chet tillarini o'rganishni rag'batlantiradi, jamoada ishlashga o'rgatadi va muloqot qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi. Bundan tashqari, bu xulosa o'z ish tajribamizdan misollar bilan tasdiqlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: samaqadorlik, manba, o'qitish usullari, faol o'qitish usuli, interfaol usul va texnikalar, talaba, o'qituvchi.

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SOME INTERACTIVE METHODS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

ANNOTATION

This article discusses the interactive method, which is one of the most effective methods in foreign language teaching system. The interactive teaching method increases motivation in learning foreign languages, making students feel more comfortable in the learning process. In addition, all the methods and techniques discussed in this article develop communication skills, teach to work in a team and listen to each other, as well as contribute to solving a specific pedagogical problem. Based on the material presented, we concluded that an interactive teaching method encourages the learning of foreign languages, teaches teamwork, and develops communication skills. In addition, this conclusion is confirmed by examples from our own experience.

Key words: production, source, teaching methods, active teaching method, interactive methods and techniques, student, teacher.

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НЕКОТОРЫЕ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается один из наиболее эффективных методов в системе обучения иностранным языкам - интерактивный метод. интерактивный метод обучения повышает мотивацию в изучении иностранных языков, ученики чувствуют себя комфортнее в процессе обучения. Кроме того, все рассмотренные в данной статье методы и приёмы развивают коммуникативные навыки, приучают работать в команде и прислушиваться друг к другу, а так же способствуют решению той или иной педагогической проблемы. На основании изложенного материала авторы приходят к выводу: интерактивный метод обучения стимулирует изучение иностранных языков, приучает работать в команде, развивает коммуникативные навыки. кроме того, данный вывод подкрепляется примерами из собственного опыта работы.

Ключевые слова: продуцирования, источник, методы обучения, активный метод обучения, интерактивные методы, приёмы, ученик, учитель.

The learning process is mainly based on two activities: transfer and acquisition of knowledge. In the first case, the teacher gives the necessary information, and the students perceive it. Innovative methods also face this process, and their purpose is to evaluate the actions of the teacher and students using new teaching avenues and methods, including new technical teaching aids.

I.D. Zvereva emphasizes that teaching methods are interactive activities aimed at achieving the educational goals of teachers and students. The teacher manages the cognitive process using a variety of sources of knowledge [8]. In addition, the methodological tactic to foreign language teaching is instigated in three ways:

- passive method;
- active method;
- interactive method.

If we talk about the passive method, then it should be noted that here the teacher is at the center of the educational process: he plays an active role, while the students are passive. Control can be done with questions, tests, etc. The the method will only be effective if used by an experienced teacher. An example of a passive method is a lecture.

Modern teaching methods are teaching methods in which the interaction, role and activity of teachers and students have the same value. For example, didactic games, analysis of concrete objects, and so on.

However, in our time, the most popular and most effective in the learning system is an interactive method or approach. The Pedagogical Encyclopedic Dictionary gives the following definition of the term: interactive - from the English word inter-action (interaction). This is a type of learning, built on the interaction of the student with the learning environment, the learning environment, which serves as an area of mastered experience [3, p. 107]. Most teachers usually understand this type of teaching as teamwork in the classroom. But here the focus should be mainly on the inner action. Students should have an inner motivation that stimulates their active work or active participation in the lesson. Teacher should guide students towards the lesson objective, which will consist of interactive activities and tasks.

Based on the data of modern pedagogy, as well as on the results obtained in the analysis of existing experience, we have identified some types of interactive methods.

Brainstorming. The generally accepted definition of the method sounds like “brainstorming” - it is a method of group, collective production of new ideas. It is used quite widely: from solving scientific, technical and creative problems to finding options for behavior in difficult social or personal situations [6, p. 54]. This is a technique for creating new ideas on a proposed topic, a method that contributes to the creative activity of students in solving problems. This technique usually provides various options for solving the problem. The communicative involvement of the student in the process is important here. The teacher must listen to all the student's positions and, without criticizing, give an objective assessment of the answer. In addition, he should encourage students to respond. If all these conditions are met, then it is possible to create a favorable learning environment when the student has the opportunity to express their ideas freely. The advantage of this method, as experience shows, is an increase in students' interest in learning a foreign language, as well as the development of creative thinking.

For a more visual example, we will give an example from our own practice. Consider a lesson in 6th grade on the topic “Present Continuous”. The problem is that students often confuse this time with Present Simple. The teacher asks the question: “What is the difference between “ I am reading a book ”and“ I read a book ”?” Students offer their own options. The final answer should be that the times of the Continuous group mean continuing actions, that is, actions that are taking place at the moment.

The next type of interactive learning of foreign languages is discussion, or discussion.

Discussion (from the Latin discussion - consideration, research) - the method of active learning, based on a public discussion of the problem, the purpose of which is to clarify and compare different points of view, to find the correct solution to a controversial issue [9]. This type of interactive learning requires the study of teaching material on a specific topic. After studying the lexical and grammatical material on the topic, students can start a discussion. This method consistently helps students and logically expresses their ideas. For this method to be effective, students should be divided into small groups, then each participant can express their ideas and take an active part in the discussion of the topic.

To achieve the effectiveness of this method, you must follow the following instructions:

- 1) the teacher, together with the students, chooses a topic for discussion;
- 2) students study the topic;
- 3) the teacher forms groups;
- 4) the teacher gives instructions;
- 5) the teacher controls the activities of the students and, if one or another assistance is needed, helps and stimulates the work;
- 6) at the end of the discussion, one participant from each group makes a presentation.

Consider a 10th grade English lesson where this method was applied. Within the framework of the covered material, we have chosen for the discussion the topic “Young people-old problems?” according to the textbook English 10–11 V.P. Kuzlev and in their work they took as a basis the text “What makes our children do this!”, Dedicated to the problem of adolescents [2, p. 114]. After all, it is known that adolescents have their own views on life, which is why they often have problems with their parents.

In order to start a discussion, it is necessary to develop the following work algorithm:

- 1) first, we will read and translate the text;
- 2) perform exercises to understand the content of the text;
- 3) we will discuss the text and pose the problem;
- 4) master the discussion vocabulary.

After all the steps are completed, the teacher must divide the students into two mini-groups and create a favorable atmosphere for discussion of the problematic topic. 5-6 pupils could speak, 3-4 minutes each. The rest of the students can complement the friend by giving their arguments.

Examples of student performance: “Teenagers have problems because they have their sights, traditions, holidays, capital England language population political system geographic position own outlook on life and the future. One of the main problems is misunderstand between parents and their

children. Nowadays, this problem is very actually. Parents try to teach us but we protest against their advice ... "

"Yes, I agree with my classmate but we also have other problems. For example, many teenagers suffer from drug addiction that is why they have problems with health. Also, smoking and drinking alcohol leads to problems ... "

Let's move on to the next type of interactive learning: a cluster (cluster).

In English, the word cluster means

"Gather in a bunch", "groups". According to the dictionary of foreign words, "a cluster is a group of any objects, distinguished in their large aggregate according to one or another characteristic" [6, p. 14].

Currently, it is one of the widely used methods of teaching a foreign language. This method can be used at any level of language learning, as well as applied in teaching both schoolchildren and older people. The essence of the method is as follows: the teacher writes a new word, and the students will pronounce the words that are combined with him.

Thus, the cluster involves all students in active work, stimulating their interest in acquiring knowledge. In addition, this method works effectively to improve monologue speech skills.

Currently, role play is of great interest in teaching foreign languages. Role play is a technique that refers to active methods of teaching practical knowledge of a foreign language [10]. Role play involves students in active work, positively influencing the internal activities of students. It creates favorable conditions for the joint work of a teacher and students, develops motivation, personal potentials of internal activity and helps to form practical skills of students.

Role-playing games promote creativity, getting out of difficult situations, and inventiveness. When using this method, you should adhere to the following instructions: the teacher needs to create a cozy atmosphere among the students who take part in the game; students should not be shy. This will help them feel more comfortable and interested in the process.

Let us give an example of a role-playing game presented by O.L. Thunderstorm "New Millennium English" for 11th grade high school: "You are invited to take part in a TV show called "Do you believe in ...?" " The show will start in 10 minutes. Take a role card and get ready to play your role. Take part in the show; try to be as active as possible. Vote on the question in the program - Do you believe in supernatural phenomena? " [1, p. 69].

Undoubtedly, role-playing games help to learn foreign languages in an entertaining way, as well as to maintain an interest in languages. Role-playing games are included in almost all textbooks and teaching aids on foreign languages.

Interactivity will be more effective if multimedia technology is used in practice. Multimedia is an innovative teaching method. This is a combination of different types of media, such as audio, video materials, presentation of presentations, with the help of which the teacher presents information to the students on an interactive whiteboard. Information technology helps the teacher motivate students to actively learn through real-world problems. The advantages of using this method are in the positive influence on the emerging speech skills. But there are also negative aspects of this approach. So, E.P. Afanasyeva writes in the article "Positive and negative aspects of using multimedia in English lessons": a large amount of information information provided by modern information means, negative impact on health. The above contradictions indicate that the use of multimedia tools in the modern process of teaching foreign languages is necessary, but requires a reasoned and balanced approach "[7, p. eleven].

Based on the above, it should be noted that the interactive teaching method increases motivation and interest in learning foreign languages, students feel comfortable in the learning process. In addition, all the methods and techniques discussed in this article develop communication skills, teach to work in a team and listen to each other, as well as contribute to solving this or that pedagogical problem..

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5 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

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